

Hybridizing Outdoor Adventure Education and Cooperative Learning in Physical Education. Students and Teachers' Views

Javier Lamoneda¹, Sixto González-Villora², Carlos Evangelio^{3*} and Javier Fernandez-Rio⁴

¹ *Consejería de Educación, Junta de Andalucía, Spain.*

² *Department of Physical Education, Arts Education, and Music. Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Spain.*

³ *Facultad de Magisterio. Universidad de Valencia, Spain*

⁴ *Educational Sciences Department, Universidad de Oviedo, Spain.*

**Corresponding author: Carlos Evangelio. Universidad de Valencia. Faculty of Magisterio of Valencia. Av. dels Tarongers, 4, 46022 València. Carlos.evangelio@uclm.es*

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Abstract

The goal of the study was to assess the effects of two different instructional frameworks (Cooperative Learning/Outdoor Adventure Education hybridization and Direct Instruction) on students' motivation and disruptive behaviours and explore students and teachers' views on hybridization. The participants were 170 high school students randomly distributed into an Experimental Group (hybridization) and a Comparison Group, and their two teachers. A quasi-experimental study, and a mixed quantitative-qualitative approach was followed. Those who experienced the hybrid model showed significantly higher intrinsic motivation and lower disruptive behaviours. The analysis of teachers and students' responses produced four positive themes (enjoyment, autonomy, novelty, motivation), one negative (workload), and other mixing different feelings (uncertainty, relatedness, learning). The hybridization showed both models complement each other. Orienteering lessons was found capable of impacting positively in the students. All students felt fully integrated into the class, promoting both the hybridization (Adventure Education and Cooperative Learning) and the content implemented (Orienteering) a shift in social hierarchies and equality among boys and girls in Physical Education.

Keywords: Disruptive behaviours; experiential education; motivation; pedagogical models.

Introduction

The use of the outdoors for educational purposes has a long tradition in many countries based on the idea that Nature can become a great educator (Sutherland & Legge, 2016). This belief is rooted in the Experiential Learning Theory (Kolb, 1984), which describes experiential learning as “the transformative process of facilitated learning which occurs between a facilitator and a participant while also emphasizing how experiences within a socially constructed environment are internalized and reflected upon to inform an individual’s future affect, behaviours and/or cognitions” (Newman, Alvarez, & Kim, 2017, p. 6). Within this framework, learning is viewed as a process of reconstruction of what is acquired from direct experiences (Knecht-Sabres, 2013). Several pedagogical approaches have emerged “under the umbrella” of the Experiential Learning Theory such as Adventure Therapy (Tucker, Norton, Itin, Hobson, & Alvarez, 2016), Outdoor/Wilderness Education (Norton & Watt, 2014), Adventure Education (Priest & Gass, 2005), Adventure Pedagogy (Newman, Kim, Tucker, & Alvarez, 2020) or Outdoor Adventure Education (OAE) as a pedagogical model in PE (Williams & Wainwright, 2016a; 2016b).

Outdoor Adventure Education

Within the Adventure Pedagogy framework (e.g. Priest & Gass, 2005; Newman et al., 2020), the term OAE was proposed as a pedagogical model to line up teacher planning and delivery and students’ learning (Williams & Wainwright, 2016a; 2016b; 2020). The goal of considering OAE as a model was to extend the models-based approach proposed by Kirk (2010), moving away from dominant instructional frameworks (i.e., Direct Instruction) or contents. Moreover, Loynes (2002) suggested a shift from a traditional focus of outdoor experiences on self-sufficiency and team goals to a new and broader view based on sustainability and egalitarianism. This new vision recognizes the risk as a fundamental

element of the model (Priest & Gass, 2005), influencing the students' physical, social, psychological and/or emotional domains (e.g. exploring new scenarios or building new relationships which can generate feelings and emotions). Therefore, Williams and Wainwright (2016a; 2016b) located OAE in traditional settings, such as trails or forests, to practice traditional activities, such as hiking or climbing. However, OAE is now considered a pedagogical model focused on including new locations (e.g. streets, urban parks, or gymnasiums), new sports (e.g. parkour, slackline, or skate), and innovative experiences (e.g. expeditions, field trips) where students can lead the way.

Notwithstanding, pedagogical models need to be grounded in learning theories / frameworks and establish critical features or elements to guide their implementation (Metzler & Colquitt, 2021). On the one hand, the underpinning framework for OAE is based on several educational schemes such as Experiential Learning Theory (the experience is the basis for the students' learning and influence their future practices; Kolb, 1984), Constructivism (the knowledge and learning is constructed by the learner through active participation) (Vygotsky, 1978) and Outdoor Environmental Education (the development of environmental awareness and relationship with planet to know we depend on it for our survival; Beames, Higgins, & Nicol, 2012). On the other hand, Williams and Wainwright (2016b) identified four non-negotiable elements of OAE as a pedagogical model: a) Being mainly outdoors: the essence of the framework, but in a technologically-driven society accessible outdoor spaces and indoor facilities can also help provide the needed experiences and drive individuals to the outdoors; b) Experiential learning: students must be directly involved in the learning process through planning how to solve the different tasks, implementing the solutions found, and evaluating them; c) Challenge by choice: students must take increasing responsibility of their learning, but teachers must help them by shifting duties to them; and d) Managed risk: an

educational tool that students must face, being this social, emotional, psychological or physical.

Although the OAE as pedagogical model has not been widely implemented, research on outdoor-based instructional frameworks have shown that access to outdoor spaces can bring global health and well-being benefits, including stress reduction (Muñoz, 2009), improvements in caring relationships not only with close friends (Quay, Dickinson, & Nettleton, 2002), and children's behaviour (Astbury & Knight, 2003). In this sense, OAE can contribute to develop social skills and cooperation among students.

Outdoor Adventure Education & Cooperative Learning

Casey and MacPhail (2018, p. 295) argued that Models-based Practice (MbP) had been based on the implementation of single models in isolation, while they believe in a “MbP approach to teach PE that involves the use of several models”. Kirk (2010) was among the first to call for a mixing or hybridization of pedagogical models to enhance the potentialities of one model alone. The connections between OAE and Cooperative Learning (CL) have a longstanding history. In a recently published review, Dyson, Howley and Wright (2020) highlighted that both models can be connected to students' social and emotional learning (reinforcing their linkage), and they called for future research involving these two and other pedagogical models.

CL has been defined as the “instructional use of small groups so that students work together to maximize their own and each other's learning” (Johnson & Johnson, 2014, p. 841). It includes five basic elements (Johnson & Johnson, 2014): (1) Positive interdependence: group members depend on each other to succeed; (2) Promotive interaction: individuals must support each other to finish the task; (3) Individual accountability: each group member must be responsible for one part of the group's work; (4) Group processing: the group must review its functioning to improve it; and (5) Interpersonal skills: individuals

must learn social skills (i.e., praise each other, share resources, be respectful...). These elements have similarities with some of the OAE non-negotiable elements such as experiential learning or challenge by choice (Jourand, Adé, Sève, Komar, & Thouvarecq, 2018), reinforcing the connections between both and the possibilities of a hybridization.

On the other hand, there exist at least four theoretical perspectives on CL (Slavin, 2014): a) Motivational: task motivation drives the learning process and individuals will only achieve their goals if the group is successful; b) Social cohesion: group cohesiveness mediates the effects of the framework on students' achievement; c) Cognitive: mental processing of information allows individuals to achieve their learning goals; and d) Developmental: interaction within the group helps members integrate critical concepts which are basic to learn and grow. In this regard, Slavin (2014) believed that the four CL perspectives can be integrated to fully explain students' enhanced learning and, concomitantly, OAE can help to: students become motivated by challenging tasks (which include risk), they rely on teammates to have success, they must process information to solve the tasks, and they must integrate key concepts to solve similar or more demanding tasks.

In this regard, Vasconcellos et al. (2019) highlighted that active methodologies or pedagogical models, such as CL, can promote students' intrinsic motivation, which is related to positive outcomes on learning (Tjeerdsma-Blankenship, 2008) and participation (Ntoumanis, 2005). Nevertheless, research on CL showed limitations on its influence on the students' affective domain, including their motivation (Casey & Goodyear, 2015). The Organismic Integration Theory, a mini-theory within the Self-Determination Theory (SDT; Ryan & Deci, 2017), highlights that individuals can show different types of motivation along a continuum that ranges from amotivation (e.g. not having any type of motivation to do an activity) to intrinsic motivation (e.g. performing an activity for the internal satisfaction obtained) (Standage, Duda, & Ntoumanis, 2005).

Finally, positive class environments or the influence of methodologies such as pedagogical models (e.g. sport education, cooperative learning or game-based approach) could be thwarted by students' disruptive behaviours, interfering with teaching and hindering the quality of education (Hsu, Li, & Pan, 2017). Several theoretical frameworks have been used to identify the determinants of students' misbehaviours. Among them, the Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1991) argues that individuals act according to social norms and their conscience under rational self-monitoring. Individuals' rationalization of the collective rules was named moral disengagement and, originally, it included eight mechanisms that can explain people's misbehaviours (Kavussanu, 2008). Its connection to students' misconducts in PE has been confirmed, and two of them, advantageous comparison (one's behaviours are compared with others' behaviours that are more severe to justify the first ones), and non-responsibility (displacement and/or diffusion of responsibility caused by social pressure and/or group action, which validates bad behaviours), positively predicted four class misbehaviours in PE settings: low engagement, failure to follow directions, poor self-management and distracting behaviour (Hsu & Pan, 2018). However, there seems to be a need for more research to fully understand the phenomenon and assess if certain methodological structures can make an impact. Methodologies such as OAE and CL seems to be relevant to improve children's behaviours in this sense (Astbury & Knight, 2003; Van Ryzin, Roseth & Biglan, 2020).

Based on the aforementioned, the goal of the present study was to compare the effects of the hybridization of OAE + Cooperative Learning (CL) versus Direct Instruction on students' motivation and disruptive behaviours. The second goal was to gain a deeper understanding assessing students and teachers' views on the hybridization and the content implemented in physical education (PE).

Method

Participants

170 students (Mage= 16.06 ± 0.73 years; 43% boys, 57% girls) enrolled in year-11 (three groups) and year-12 (four groups) of one high school in southern Spain and their two PE teachers agreed to participate. The school administration randomly distributed the students in the groups and assigned their PE teacher. The goal was to conduct the study in a non-manipulated context. The Experimental Group (EG; 94 students; two year-11 and two year-12 groups) experienced a hybrid CL + OAE learning unit, while the Comparison Group (CG; 76; one year-11 and two year-12 groups) experienced Direct Instruction (DI). None of the students had experienced pedagogical models before. Both participating teachers taught classes in each study group (EG, CG). They were familiar with the new methodological frameworks, but their practical experience was very limited. Non-probabilistic, convenience sampling was used (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2011).

Design and procedure

A quasi-experimental, pre-test, post-test, comparison group research design and a mixed method (quantitative-qualitative) approach were used (Cohen et al., 2011). The protocol was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki and the ethical guidelines of the American Psychological Association. First, permission from the University of Castilla-La Mancha Ethics Committee was obtained. Second, the study was approved by the research commission of Junta de Andalucía (Spain). Third, the project was fully explained to the target school's administrators as well as the families/legal guardians: goals, length and implications. The design included that the participating class-groups would be randomly selected to complete one of the two selected programs (CL + OAE, DI) and at the end of the study, the class-groups would be shifted between the two programs to experience both approaches. Finally, a written consent was obtained from all of them.

Intervention programmes

Hastie and Casey (2014, p. 423) considered that fidelity of the intervention programs should be provided: “(a) a rich description of the curricular elements of the unit, (b) a detailed validation of model implementation and (c) a detailed description of the program context”.

Regarding the third one, both study groups experienced the same lesson, orienteering, during the same length: seven weeks (55-minute sessions; two sessions/week; 14 sessions). The only difference was that the EG experienced a hybrid CL + OAE methodological approach, while the CG DI (see Table 1). Regarding the rich description of the curricular elements, the EG experienced a hybrid CL + OAE program. It included the previously mentioned five main elements of CL (Johnson & Johnson, 2014): face-to-face promotive interaction (e.g. students worked in groups to design their own orienteering race), positive interdependence (e.g. students had to help each other finish the EduCoop-Escape Room [escape rooms, which include CL features to solve challenges in groups cooperatively; for example, making group decisions or helping each other; see more in Fernández-Río, 2018] made with orienteering tasks), individual accountability (e.g. each student was responsible of a part in the final assignment I), interpersonal and small-group skills (e.g. team members cheered each other during group orienteering), and group processing (e.g. groups were encouraged to assess their functioning). Since the EG had never experienced CL, it was introduced using the “cooperative learning cycle” framework (Fernandez-Rio, 2016): Phase I to build group cohesion (sessions 1-5), Phase II to integrate CL as a content using simple techniques (e.g. coop-play, collective score, pairs-check-perform) (session 6), and Phase III to

use CL as a framework through complex techniques (e.g. Puzzle¹, learning groups) (sessions 7-13). This program also included basic OAE elements (Sutherland & Legge, 2016; Williams & Wainwright, 2016a; 2020; Zmudy, Curtner-Smith, & Steffen, 2009): team building and group development (e.g. students worked in small, heterogeneous groups and team building activities were conducted in sessions 1-5), experiential learning (e.g. some activities were conducted directly in the outdoors: nearby parks, trails), reviewing (e.g. group members discussed and processed the information), controlled risk (e.g. some risk was included); and challenge by choice (e.g. students were asked to design tasks to show their commitment). Both models merged to provide a student-centred context where responsibility was partially shifted from the teacher to the students (e.g. session 7: students learned how to use a compass through Jigsaw; session 8: students used 'learning teams' to solve tasks using the compass).

On the other hand, the CG experienced a DI approach: teacher-centred (the teacher controlled the tempo and provided all the information), learning drills (no games or challenges, just tasks), competition (conducted in sessions 10-12 to promote learning), performance-oriented (rewards were handed based on performance in competitive tasks). The basic lesson structure was warm-up, main part, and cool-down. Students focused on participation (no debrief) and groups changed daily, selected by the teacher. Therefore, task selection and presentation, organization, lessons' basic framework, pacing and evaluation were all teacher-centred (Metzler & Colquitt, 2021).

Two PE teachers implemented both programmes (they taught class-groups belonging to the CG and the EG). They both had more than 10 years of professional experience, and

¹ Puzzle (Jigsaw; Aronson, 1978): A cooperative learning technique where each group member is responsible for learning a piece of content and become the group's expert in that piece; next, the experts get together to learn; and finally, each expert returns to his or her initial group to teach the rest of group.

they were knowledgeable on Orienteering. They had been previously involved in projects on educational innovation. To conduct the present study, they contacted two university researchers with more than 10 years on experience on pedagogical models' theory and practice.

[Insert Table 1 near here]

To implement the content (orienteering) in both groups, some materials from the International Orienteering Federation were adapted and used. For example, the official orienteering maps with numbered controls to follow an order were modified to provide groups more choice on how to solve them (to foster group processing and communicative skills). Other resources were created specifically for the intervention, such as the group's commitment pact or the students' credential to participate. On the other hand, teachers used the external locations of the school (e.g. the school' sports centre or other outdoor spaces) and outside locations near to the school (e.g. parks or green areas) (Table 1 shows the sequence of use of these locations). Therefore, the content was adapted to the requirements of the school and its nearby outdoors context.

Finally, regarding validation of model implementation, two procedures were used. First, the university researchers, experts on pedagogical models, carefully supervised all lessons of the EG and CG. They were in close contact with the participating teachers via skype, e-mail, WhatsApp, and mobile phone to work on the final version of both learning units. This period included 5 hours of theory and 30 hours of practice on CL and OAE to review possible tasks and pre-designed sessions and obtain a first draft of the hybrid learning unit. This was implemented in a group of students similar to the target population (pilot study) to assess its adequacy. Information from this experience was used to modify the initial learning unit and design the final one. During the implementation phase, the research team met on-line on several

occasions to assess and provide feedback. Goodyear's (2017) continuous professional development framework was followed to support the project, which included participatory action research: a) dialogue with experienced university professors on pedagogical models that provided feedback and support, and b) analysis of practice through on-line group meetings. The second procedure used to assess model implementation included a researcher (expert on pedagogical models and totally blind to the study) who observed one out of every three lessons on both groups. He assessed both pedagogical models using a pre-existing checklist (Fernandez-Rio, Sanz, Fernandez-Cando, & Santos, 2017), obtaining a 100% match. He was also in charge of determine that the participating teacher, who taught both study groups, did not act in favour of one of the intervention groups.

[Insert Table 2 near here]

Measurements

Quantitative

The subscale *Intrinsic Motivation* of the Spanish validated version of the *Revised Perceived Locus of Causality Scale in PE* (Vlachopoulos, Katartzi, Kontou, Moustaka & Goudas, 2011) was used. It includes four items (i.e., “because it is fun”) preceded by the stem: “I participate in the PE class...”. Participants responded in a Likert scale from (1) not true at all to (7) totally true. Cronbach's α value were .85 at the pre-test and .86 at the post-test.

The Spanish validated version of the *PE Classroom Instrument* (Krech, Kulinna, & Cothran, 2010) was used to assess *disruptive behaviours*. The Krech et al.'s (2010) instrument has been previously used to assess students' misbehaviours by authors such as Hsu et al. (2017). It includes five subscales: *aggressive* (e.g., “I intimidate my classmates”), *low engagement* (e.g., “I am lazy in class”), *fails to follow directions* (e.g., “I do not line up

right”), *distracts/disturbs others* (e.g., “I do not pay attention”) and *low self-management* (e.g., “I am a smart mouth”). All items were prefaced by the sentence: “Think about your own behaviour in the PE class”. Participants responded in a Likert scale from (1) never to (5) always. Cronbach’s α was .606 in pre-test and .632 in post-test, which is still considered a valid score when the number of items is limited (Cohen et al., 2011).

Qualitative

Open-ended questions. At the end of the intervention program, students were asked to answer a few questions about the learning (15-20 minutes) unit they had just experienced (e.g., “from the teaching received, what has it given you?”). All comments and reflections were obtained on-line (digital documents completed by students). They were asked to be honest and reflect positive and negative issues because answers were anonymous. The goal was to obtain first-hand information from the “main character”.

Teachers’ interview. At the completion of the intervention program, the participating teachers engaged in an open-dialogue session (non-structured interview) supported by the research team. The goal was to exchange views, ideas or feelings about the hybrid program (e.g., “What positive and negative aspects of teaching do you remember?”). The session (1 hour) was recorded and transcribed.

Data analysis

All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS 20.0. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to check whether data was normally distributed, and it showed that it was not. However, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) is considered a valid statistical procedure under non-normality conditions when skewness and kurtosis range between -1 and 1 (Blanca, Alarcón, Arnau, Bono, & Bendayan, 2017), and these were -.222 and .188. Therefore, a Multiple ANOVA was conducted to assess initial homogeneity among groups. Then, descriptive and

inferential analyses were conducted, including a multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA), with the two-level group variable (control, experimental), to assess the effects of the intervention program).

Qualitative data obtained through the different instruments were analysed with the help of MAXQDA 11, using content analysis and constant comparison (Libarkin & Kurdziel, 2002). Cross-pattern analysis of the transcribed texts was used to code the most concurring text extracts, and group them into categories and subcategories (Saldaña, 2009). The ones that emerged in the first independent analyses were critically examined by the research team through thoughtful dialogue. Reliability was supported through continuous feedback and participatory analysis by the research team, reviewing the different categories. Several criteria have been proposed to guarantee the quality of qualitative research (Sparkes & Smith, 2014), and three were used: (1) Credibility: peer debriefing among the authors of the document to assess the extent the event under analysis represented the participants' experience; authors met to discuss data interpretation. (2) Transferability: a deep description of the participants' background, data collection process, and data analysis procedure to enable other researchers and scholars transfer this study to other contexts. (3) Confirmability: teachers received a transcription of their responses to verify correctness of the data, clarify confusing quotes, and add information when necessary to confirm that data, analysis and results were based in the participants' experiences.

Results

Quantitative

The results of the MANOVA pre-test showed that there were no differences between study groups: Wilk's $\lambda=.96$, $F(6, 166)=1.19$, $p=.31$. Regarding the effects produced by the intervention program, the MANCOVA revealed significant differences between both groups:

Wilk's $\lambda = .92$, $F(6, 156) = 2.14$, $p < .05$. Subsequent ANOVAS showed statistically significant differences favouring the EG in three variables: *intrinsic motivation*: $F(1, 167) = 5.76$, $p = .018$, *fails to follow directions*: $F(1, 167) = 7.11$, $p < .008$, and *distracts/disturbs others*: $F(1, 167) = 6.18$, $p = .014$ (Table 2). No significant differences were obtained based on gender or grade.

[Insert Table 3 near here]

Qualitative

From the joined analysis of the teachers and the students' responses, eight themes emerged. Four grouped codes related to positive responses: *enjoyment*, *autonomy*, *novelty*, *motivation*; one grouped to negative: *workload*; and three included mixed views: *uncertainty*, *relatedness*, and *learning*. Moreover, some themes were shared by students and teachers (*autonomy*, *uncertainty*) (Figure 1). Themes are presented below with the number of meaningful extracts, and quotes are used to exemplify. Those from the students' open-ended questions were coded EGOE for the experimental group and CGOE for the control group, and those from the teachers' interview TIT1 and TIT2.

[Insert Figure 1 near here]

The most frequently mentioned theme in the EG was *Relatedness* (188 extracts), but not in the CG (88 extracts). However, students described positive and negative views.

"It [program] helped improve coexistence and be closer to my classmates" (Nuria, EGOE)

"The unit allowed me to strengthen my relationship with my teammates" (Elías, CGOE)

"I did not like to interact with people I did not get along with" (Ana, EGOE)

“I prefer to practice orienteering alone. Some people are lazy and do not work well” (Elena, CGOE).

These results showed different perceptions from the students on the programmes experienced, probably due to the differences on their responsibility while performing the activities, which negatively influenced some relationships. However, both teachers emphasized the psycho-social impact of the experimental program in the students:

“I have seen a clear positive evolution in the EG’s dynamics, but not in the CG. These students (CG) were bored at the end and their irresponsibility continued” (TIT1).

“Initially, lack of respect for others, lack of discipline and irresponsibility in the tasks. As the program (EG) evolved, these problems went gradually away thanks to the cooperative environment, which helped build social intra-group skills. It works better than the traditional approach” (TIT2).

The cooperation among students improved the class climate and social skills to work all together. In this sense, teachers also emphasized that the content was appropriate to work on co-education and acknowledged no gender differences:

“I did not see any gender or skill-based preferences. The students enjoyed working with one another” (TIT1).

“I could not see that the girls or the boys enjoyed the learning unit more or less” (TIT2).

Enjoyment was the second highest ranked theme in the EG (160 extracts) and the first in the CG (118 extracts). Students from both groups, and both teachers, overwhelmingly believed that the learning unit was enjoyable, showing that the new framework had been a complete success:

“All activities have been very exciting and entertaining” (Pablo, EGOE)

“I prefer alternative teaching methods because you enjoy the subject more. Everyone takes it in their own way (as long as it is taken seriously)” (Luisa, EGOE).

“It was fun to guide myself using a map” (Marcos, CGOE).

“They [students] had a good time” (TIT1).

“They [students] showed excitement, emotion, joy... These experiences are different from those they can get from mobile phones or substances [drugs]... very positive” (TIT2).

The feeling of enjoyment on the students was a key element to increase their involvement in the lessons, seeking to participate autonomously. Thus, *autonomy* was also a very “popular” theme (EG = 133 extracts, CG = 102 extracts). Students in the CG felt that the content (orienteering) had promoted their autonomy in class, while students in the EG felt that the instructional framework (CL+OAE) had done it:

“I enjoyed the alternative methodology, because it gives more freedom, I do not like to be under control, it makes me feel more relaxed, more comfortable in class” (Judith, EGOE).

“When they give you freedom and the student is respectful, we can do incredible things” (Juan, EGOE).

“I’d rather perform physical activity in the outdoors because I feel more free, more relaxed. It helps you disconnect from the world” (Lucas, CGOE).

Moreover, students’ autonomy helped the teachers conduct the lessons because orienteering requires so much space and the teacher could not supervise all students at the same time. This theme also came out in the teachers’ comments:

“The class dynamic in the EG was better, because they [students] knew what they had to do” (TIT1).

“You [teacher] give a lot of autonomy to the students, both in the use of resources and in the use of the space, freely with a map, in areas where you [teacher] are not in control, outside the school” (TIT2).

On the other hand, the theme *Novelty* came out in many students’ comments (EG = 82 extracts, CG = 78) because both, the content for the CG and the methodology for the EG, were innovative elements in their classes:

"I think this has been our best year. We have worked in a different way than we were used to. We have learned by ourselves and learned to work as a team. I feel that I have learned more than previous years" (Ana, EGOE).

“I liked Orienteering because is something different that we have never done. It is not the same as always” (Elena, EGOE).

“It [content] is different the others, because it makes you face unusual scenarios and objectives, which makes it interesting” (Jaime, CGOE).

The autonomy transferred from teachers to students was guided by an increase in their learning which helped them assume responsibilities. Nevertheless, *learning* was the second theme that included negative and positive comments (EG = 71 extracts, CG = 67 extracts):

“It [program] has been one of the best activities that I have ever experienced in PE. I have learned a lot” (Pilar, EGOE)

“It [unit] has given me the opportunity to learn and appreciate everything more” (Héctor, CGOE).

“I didn’t enjoy the first few sessions searching for beacons, because I had problems understanding the maps and we couldn’t find a thing” (Mateo, CGOE).

The novelty of the content impacted students’ learning because some of them find it interesting and challenging, but other disliked their lack of experience in this unusual content:

“A few students believed that some content was challenging, probably, because it was completely new for them: I did not like the compass, it was difficult to use” (Rosa, EGOE)

Teacher guidelines in the CG helped these students with difficulties solve the tasks, while those in the EG did it more autonomously. From the teachers’ point of view, the novelty of the methodology was a challenge, but its implementation was positive for their professional development:

“Very enriching... try hard to learn new teaching approaches is always positive” (TIT1)

“Everything was positive... the effort to implement a new program was good for me, because it will improve my background as a teacher. It helps you grow also as an individual” (TIT2).

On the other hand, to apply unusual methodological frameworks caused some unknown feelings and responses. *Uncertainty* (EG = 28 extracts, CG = 50 extracts) was a theme mentioned by students and teachers with positive and negative comments. Regarding to

the students' responses, some of them believed that some activities had made them feel insecure and they liked more orienteering in nearby, simple, and familiar spaces, but other considered it exciting:

"I prefer to practice orienteering in urban areas; very few times I have done it in natural areas... I can get lost" (Abel, EGOE).

"What I liked the least was to run individually. I felt unsafe" (Nuria, CGOE).

Furthermore, some students (EG = 20 extracts, CG = 45 extracts) believed that the uncertainty caused by the content and the outdoor (e.g. vegetation, distance, unknown territory/content) was positive:

"This content is more difficult, but I find it more interesting and fun" (Santiago, CGOE)

"I prefer orienteering in natural spaces where you must cross rivers, go up-hill and down-hill, vegetation is a troublesome... because the risk is exciting" (Luis, EGOE).

In relation to the teachers' views, they also felt that the new instructional approach (CL+OAE) brought uncertainty to their pedagogical practice:

"...it has been difficult to implement the roles, the challenges, the students' autonomy... I was not used to it; I felt insecure" (TIT2)

"There were quite a few moments of uncertainty during the implementation: conflict resolution within the cooperative groups, guide groups towards the final project. It has difficult" (TIT1).

The only negative theme that emerged from the teachers' responses was *workload*.

Both teachers acknowledged that the hybrid CL+OAE pedagogical approach had greatly increased their involvement preparing the intervention and taking into account pedagogical considerations related to the models:

"The extra workload has been the price that one [teacher] has to pay to make this [program] real" (TIT1)

"The hybrid program demanded great involvement and effort from us [teachers]" (TIT2).

Nevertheless, the teachers concluded that the work done to prepare the intervention, as well as the features of the instructional framework and the content had promoted students'

Motivation:

“They [students] were highly motivated in the EG, eager to work; they asked me to review the final assignment several times before turning it in” (TIT1)

“Students were hypermotivated; they were eager to work on their own; they were not concern about the grades. It was very positive” (TIT2).

Discussion

The first goal of the study was to assess the effects of two instructional frameworks (CL + OAE; Direct Instruction) on students' motivation and disruptive behaviours. Results showed that those who experienced the hybrid model showed significantly higher intrinsic motivation, and significantly lower two disruptive behaviours (*fails to follow directions, distracts/disturbs others*). The second goal was to assess students and teachers' views on a hybrid CL-OAE orienteering learning unit and eight themes emerged; most positive: *enjoyment, autonomy, novelty, motivation*; one negative: *workload*; and three included mixed views: *uncertainty, relatedness, and learning*. Moreover, some were shared by students and teachers (*autonomy, uncertainty*).

Regarding the first goal, only the hybrid CL + OAE program positively impacted students' intrinsic motivation, which emerged, both, in the quantitative and the qualitative results. Previous studies found that outdoor programs can increase students' motivation and enthusiasm (Dyment, Morse, Shaw, & Smith, 2014), as well as CL (Fernandez-Rio et al., 2017). These results could contribute cautiously to shed light on the limitation of studies that specifically evaluate the influence of CL on the affective domain (Casey & Goodyear, 2015), considering that it has been hybridized with OAE.

In the present study, both pedagogical models joined “forces” to positively impact students’ motivation. Vasconcellos et al. (2019) highlighted the strong correlation between autonomous motivation (intrinsic) and individuals’ basic psychological needs, and in this study, students who experienced the hybrid model mentioned more frequently two of them, *autonomy* and *relatedness*. Competence was not directly analysed or categorized but it has been related to the *learning* acquired by students to integrate the content autonomously and responsibly. Two key elements helped create an autonomous supportive class context, where social interactions were fundamental: challenge by choice or experiential learning: students taking increasing responsibility of their learning and teachers help shifting duties to them (Williams & Wainwright, 2016a); and individual accountability or positive interdependence: group members had a part in the group’s task, and one depended on the others’ success (Slavin, 2014).

Moreover, students in the hybrid model were asked to work in small, heterogeneous groups during the whole learning unit. Peer support has been previously connected to the satisfaction of students’ basic psychological needs (Vasconcellos et al., 2019) and improve children’s social behaviours (Van Ryzin et al., 2019). Again, elements like reviewing (OAE) or group processing and interpersonal skills (CL) probably helped promote peer support along the unit and results confirmed it. Final evidence of the autonomous learning environment created in the hybrid unit was that the theme *autonomy* emerged from, both, students and teachers’ comments. Therefore, the previously discussed quantitative and qualitative outcomes (motivation, autonomy, relatedness, learning) of the new approach (CL + OAE) engaged students more than the traditional DI approach. This finding clearly challenges conventional instructional methods like DI, which can also produce positive outcomes, but to a lesser extent (Bessa, Hastie, Ramos & Mesquita, 2021). Teachers should use new

pedagogical approaches like the hybrid CL + OAE to produce a greater impact in their students providing them more relevant and meaningful experiences (Bähr & Wibowo, 2012).

The second goal was to assess students and teachers' views on a hybrid CL + OAE learning unit. *Novelty* and *enjoyment* have been highlighted as important outcomes in OAE (Sutherland & Legge, 2016) and it was not different in the present study. Moreover, they were highlighted similarly by students from both study groups, indicating that both learning conditions were found positive. Regarding the first one, Orienteering is considered a popular PE content in countries with a long tradition in outdoor education programs, but not in Spanish educational context. Students considered that the content (in CG and EG) and the methodological approach (EG) were novel, because they had never experienced Orienteering or the hybrid CL + OAE framework, respectively. Novelty has been identified as a basic psychological need within the self-determination theory (Gonzalez-Cutre, Sicilia, Sierra, Ferriz, & Hagger, 2016), and it has been connected to an increase in students' intrinsic motivation in programs based on new pedagogical approaches like Gamification (Fernandez-Rio, de las Heras, Gonzalez, Trillo, & Palomares, 2020). Results from the present study provides support to the idea that students need novelty in their classes to enjoy them and increase their motivation. Active engagement and learning (Mui, Carpio, & Ong, 2019) have been connected to novelty and engagement in educational contexts, and both were integral part of the CL + OAE program.

Some themes that emerged from the analyses were considered positive and negative at the same time. Among them, *uncertainty* was mentioned by students and teachers for different reasons. The first ones, both in the CG and the EG, believed that the context had made them feel insecure. The fourth non-negotiable element of OAE is risk management (Williams & Wainwright, 2016b), and the combination of novel contents to the students (Orienteering), conducted in new contexts (outdoors), under different pedagogical approaches (CL + OAE)

forced students to face social, emotional, psychological, and physical risk, and supposed a way forward suggested (Williams & Wainwright, 2020). They all bring some degree of *uncertainty* and students had to face all possible fears or challenges that could be presented to him. Previous research indicated that when students build success over those stressful environments their motivation increases (Williams & Wainwright, 2016a; 2016b). Results from the present study supported this idea because only students in the EG increased their intrinsic motivation, and *uncertainty* was mentioned. However, uncertainty was also found positive, interesting, fun, exciting because of the outdoors (i.e., vegetation, distance, unknown territory/content). Therefore, it should be considered a content that can engage the students, challenging traditional contents like indoor sports. On the other hand, teachers' *uncertainty* was also connected to risk and fear, but it came from the novel pedagogical approach used in the EG. Both teachers were familiar with the methodological frameworks (CL and OAE), but they had never put into practice the hybrid model or participated in a study. Therefore, worries came out in their comments. This is important, because conducting new pedagogical approaches can be challenging and teachers need external support to promote continuous professional development (Goodyear, 2017). Connected to this issue, the second negative theme that emerged only among teachers was *workload*. They considered that it had increased with the hybrid program. The use of novel pedagogical approaches has been associated with an increase in the teachers' workload because they demand an active involvement from the teachers (Fernandez-Rio et al., 2020).

Other themes that were considered positive and negative at the same time (although not with the same weight): were *relatedness* and *learning*. The first one raised some negative comments probably because small, heterogeneous groups were an integral part of the hybrid unit and grouping can be problematic. The goal is always to build groups with functional diversity and a wide range of skills and problem-solving perspectives that can benefit the

group. There is an ongoing debate between friendship and heterogeneous grouping in CL. Results suggest that both have the potential to promote high-order social and cognitive learning, but low-skilled students prefer friendship grouping (O’Leary, Barber, & Keane, 2019). In this study, heterogeneous grouping was used, and it probably caused some students to feel that they/others did not fit in the group; specially, since they were not used to group work. On the other hand, *learning* also emerged as a negative theme for some students both in the CG and the EG. As previously mentioned, Orienteering is not a popular lesson in PE in Spain and it was completely new to all the students. From their responses, it is easy to deduce that it was very difficult for some (especially the use of the compass). Teachers should be aware that students’ progress at different pace, and it should be carefully considered when dealing with contents with no “tradition”.

Finally, it is very important to highlight that no differences were found based on gender on any of the variables assessed. Therefore, the environment created helped both, girls and boys, become fully integrated in the PE class. On the one hand, pedagogical models such as CL promotes the participation of all the students, regardless of their gender, fostering the involvement and the individual responsibility of all (Goodyear et al., 2014; Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2018), and it showed in the results. Likewise, previous research found that participants in OAE activities “felt than the usual social hierarchies and masculinities were non-existent and when they did develop, they shifted based on specific skills needed” (Sutherland & Legge, 2016, p. 305). Finally, some outdoor contents (Kennedy & Russel, 2021) and other contents (Hastie & Casey, 2014) have been viewed as frameworks that support hegemonic masculinity, privileging highly-skilled males. Results from the present study supported the idea that Orienteering can help create inclusive frameworks, showing that more democratic ways of PE are possible. Again, it should be considered a content that can

engage girls and boys alike, challenging traditional contents and making a bigger impact in every student.

In conclusion, CL and OAE were found two pedagogical models that complemented each other to produce positive outcomes. Similarly, Orienteering was found a content in PE capable of impacting positively in the students. Most important, girls and boys felt fully integrated in the class, promoting both the hybrid model (CL + OAE) and the content a shift in social hierarchies and masculinities in PE. Unfortunately, both also produced negative and mixed feelings that need to be considered.

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Biographical notes

Javier Lamedona Prieto. Physical Education teacher at Junta de Andalucía, Spain. Doctor in sports science with research in educational intervention with young people.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9833-4804>

Sixto González-Víllora. Associate Professor at Faculty of Education (Albacete) and Academic Director of the Vice-Rector's Office for Science Policy at the University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain. His research focuses on models-based practice, teacher

learning/research and youth sport (focus on decision-making). <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-2473-5223>

Carlos Evangelio. Doctor in Physical Education, currently at the Faculty of Teacher Education of the University of Valencia. He is hired through a contract of Requalification “Margarita Salas” funded by the University of Castilla-La Mancha (MS2021). His lines of research focuses on models-based practices. <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-5461-2588>.

Javier Fernandez-Rio. Professor at the Faculty of Teacher Training and Education and area director for Sport and Health at the University of Oviedo, Spain. His lines of research include pedagogical models. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1368-3723>

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Figure 1.

Teachers and students' themes.

Table 1.

Intervention programmes.

Week	Session	Comparison Group Direct Instruction	Experimental Group CL-OAE
1	1	Pre-test questionnaires and presentation of the unit	Pre-test questionnaires and presentation of the unit
	2	Basic orienteering ideas and tips	CL phase 1: presentation, break the ice and outdoor education basics
2	3	Map design and use	CL phase 1: trust one another, map use
	4	Initial assessment: individual orienteering	CL phase 1: get to know yourself; initial assessment: group orientation
3	5	Orienteering race I: training, memorization....	CL phase 1: group initiatives; orienteering in groups: training, memorization...
	6	Orienteering race II: score test	CL phase 2: orienteering in groups (coop-play, collective score, pairs-check-perform)
4	7	Learn to use a compass	CL phase 3: learn to use a compass(puzzle)
	8	Use a compass: individual practical test	Use a compass: practical test in an educoop-scaperoom (learning groups)
5	9	Prepare the outdoor competition and the final assignment	Prepare a co-existence day in the outdoor and the final assignment (learning groups)
	10	Intra-school individual competition in the outdoor; awards based on age and gender	Co-existence day in the outdoor; heterogeneous groups based on age, gender, skill (learning groups)
6	11	Final assignment I: intra-class individual orienteering competition	Final assignment I: design your own orienteering adventure raid in groups (learning groups)
	12	Final assignment I: intra-class individual orienteering competition	Final assignment I: design your own orienteering adventure raid; group presentation (learning groups)
7	13	Final assignment II: design an orienteering race (individual)	Final assignment II: personal diary and text comments
	14	Post-test questionnaires	Post-test questionnaires

Note: Cooperative learning techniques used are included in the CL-OAE unit between brackets.

Table 2.

Checklist to check the fidelity of the models applied.

Items	Yes	No
1. Students' groups change from one session to the other		
2. Students' groups are maintained throughout the unit		
3. Students warm up in a large group		
4. Students warm up in groups and work on group development		
5. Tasks are conducted by the teacher		
6. Tasks are conducted by the students		

Note: items 1, 3, 5 represent Direct Instruction; items 2, 4, 6 represent Cooperative Learning-Outdoor Adventure Education.

Table 3.

Results of quantitative instruments on students' motivation and disruptive behaviours.

	Pre-test				Post-test				Post-test ANCOVA			
	Experimental		Control		Experimental		Control		F (1,171)	p	η^2	P
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD				
Intrinsic motivation	5.43	1.32	5.12	1.54	5.61	1.23	5.11	1.50	5.76	.018	.03	.66
Low engagement	1.77	.58	1.89	.65	1.61	.65	1.82	.59	2.17	.143	.01	.31
Fails to follow directions	1.46	.58	1.44	.57	1.34	.48	1.55	.63	7.11	.008	.04	.75
Distracts/disturbs others	1.29	.39	1.40	.47	1.25	.36	1.47	.49	6.18	.014	.04	.69
Low self-management	1.69	.45	1.79	.47	1.69	.53	1.77	.48	0.08	.774	.00	.06
Aggressive	1.46	.48	1.55	.52	1.49	.63	1.63	.55	1.01	.317	.01	.17

Note: M: Mean; SD: standard deviation; $p < .05$; η^2 : effect size; P: Power.